

TUMOR-INFILTRATING LYMPHOCYTE THERAPY ON ADVANCED MELANOMA

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Tumor Infiltrating Lymphocyte [TIL] therapy is one of the modern innovative personalized treatment technique in which the immune cells like lymphocytes are harvested from the tumor ,multiplied into billions in a laboratory using interleukin-2 and then again injected back into the same person by promoting their self -immune response against the tumor. It is now being introduced to treat one of the most lethal malignant skin tumor called melanoma which is a tumor of melanocytes.

Goals and Objectives: It is important to study about this new innovative technique of treatment on melanoma as this malignancy gives only a maximum survival rate of 5 years. And also it has a good response over the patients who had failed immunotherapy in advanced stages. The main goal is to increase the lifespan of those patients using TIL therapy.

Materials and methods:

Research articles and literature review have been revised to give a better view in the results. And also some statistical and comparative data provided by pubmed and google scholar are also used .

Results of the study:

Scientific researches have shown that this TIL therapy have shown good improvement and survival rate of those patients who has melanoma in their advanced stages as well. And the studies shows that the patients who has serious metastatic tumors not responding to the immunotherapy with Iplimumab, a monoclonal antibody responds to this TIL therapy which comprise both CD4+ and CD8+ T cells which recognizes the particular tumor associated antigens as those immune cells are produced from the lymphocytes driven from those tumors. It got an objective rate response of 31% to 36% with a median response duration of approximately 36 months but it varies according to the severity of the metastasis. It shows that one who got previous immunotherapy along with an anti PD L-1 treatment shows lesser efficacy than the TIL therapy. Even though it increases the lifespan of those patients who are in the edge of their life ,it has side effects which is minimum compared to death. Mostly it got side effects of hematological conditions like low platelet count, anemia and also fever, chills also found in patients due to those immune responses driven by the lymphocytes. There are some recent researches are also going on the efficiency of involving TIL therapy in other cancers like cervical cancer caused by HPV and also in lung cancers as well. Still the researches are going on this treatment regarding this adaptive personalized immune response to increase the year of survival and also this therapy is still experimental in other non- melanoma cancers.

Conclusion:

Tumor Infiltrating Lymphocyte therapy [TIL therapy] have shown some promising improvement in the durability of their life than any other methods and also who got remission . But there are some limitations in this technique as it is available only in some countries like UK and USA. It is quite expensive than other techniques. **Prevention is better than cure** , so that minimizing the risk factors like applying sunscreen and avoiding tanning lamps decrease the UV exposure ,thereby decreasing the chances of getting melanoma.